

MEASURING ATTACHMENT IN THE WORKPLACE THROUGH PICTURES

MERANIE VZŤAHOVEJ VÄZBY NA PRACOVISKU PROSTREDNÍCTVOM OBRÁZKOV

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Abstract:

In this study, we focused on presenting the process of creating a questionnaire method for measuring attachment styles at the workplace through the use of ambiguous images. The sample consisted of 129 participants from working adults, primarily students. The selection was made online based on the principle of available choice. The Workplace Attachment self-assessment questionnaire items were assigned to ambiguous pictures in threes. Three statements representing three attachment styles (secure attachment to leader, avoidant attachment to peers, anxious attachment to leader and peers) were assigned to each picture. The participants had to choose only one statement from the three statements offered for the picture. They had to select the statement that best describes the situation in the picture. The total number of 41 images was reduced to 8, while only those images with three statements were selected, in which the participants selected each statement with a frequency of approximately 30%. All attachment styles were moderately significantly and negatively correlated with each other. These correlations expressed the frequencies of the selection of statements and were thus logically negatively related to each other. These correlations did not reflect associations between attachment styles per se. No attachment style stood out above the others here, as evidenced by a selection of images that, on average, do not favor any attachment styles. This method should ensure the individual uniqueness of the individual's choice. In further research, it would be appropriate to verify the convergent validity of the questionnaire.

Keywords: attachment in the workplace; attachment styles; secure attachment; leader; colleagues; pictures

Abstrakt:

V tejto štúdií sme sa zamerali na predstavenie procesu tvorby dotazníkovej metódy na meranie vzťahovej väzby na pracovisku, prostredníctvom využitia mnohoznačných obrázkov. Vzorku tvorilo 129 participantov z radov dospelých pracujúcich, prevažne študentov. Výber bol uskutočnený online formou na princípe dostupného výberu. Položky sebaopisujúceho dotazníka Pripútania na pracovisku boli vždy v trojiciach priradené k mnohoznačným obrázkom. Ku každému obrázku boli priradené tri výroky, reprezentujúce tri štýly pripútania (bezpečné pripútanie k lídrovi, vyhýbavé pripútanie ku kolegom, úzkostné pripútanie k lídrovi a ku kolegom). Participanti mali vybrať z troch ponúknutých výrokov vždy len jeden výrok k obrázku. Mali vybrať výrok, ktorý podľa nich najlepšie vystihuje situáciu na obrázku. Celkový počet 41 obrázkov bol zredukovaný na 8, pričom boli vybrané len tie obrázky s trojicou výrokov,

v ktorých participanti vybrali každý výrok približne vo frekvencii 30%. Všetky škály pripútanie medzi sebou korelovali stredne významne a negatívne. Tieto korelácie vyjadrovali početnosti výberu výrokov a teda logicky súviseli navzájom negatívne. Tieto korelácie nevyjadrovali súvislosti medzi štýlmi pripútania ako takými. Žiaden štýl pripútania tu nevynikal nad inými, čo vyplýva z voľby obrázkov, ktoré v priemere nezvýhodňujú žiaden zo štýlov pripútania. Tento spôsob by mal zaistiť individuálnu jedinečnosť voľby jednotlivca. V ďalšom výskume by bolo vhodné overiť konvergentnú validitu dotazníka.

Kľúčové slová: pripútanie na pracovisku; štýly pripútania; bezpečné pripútanie; líder; kolegovia; obrázky

INTRODUCTION

Hazan and Shaver (1990) were the first to transfer empirically the idea that the relationship between attachment type in adulthood and work orientation resembles the dynamics of attachment and exploration in childhood, suggesting that attachment type carries over into people's work lives and can be present throughout life. Hazan and Shaver (1990) measured the type of attachment in romantic relationships by having participants choose one of three options that characterized the perception of their relationships in adulthood. They were based on the description of the types of attachment styles according to M. Ainsworth (1978). In the discussion, they stated that there are few descriptions of behavior patterns in the work environment depending on the attachment style. For example, they cite a feeling of mistrust in others and reluctance to take vacations with avoidant people; procrastination, pandering for praise, or dreaming of success in people with anxious/ambivalent attachment.

Bartholomew and Horowitz (1991) assumed that attachment is related to models of representation of self and others as an expression of expectations, beliefs, and strategies that people have about loved ones in general and attachment figures in particular. Based on a combination of self and other perceptions, they defined four categories of attachment: secure, preoccupied, fearful-avoidant, and dismissing-avoidant. They developed the Relationship Questionnaire (RQ), a short instrument containing descriptions of four attachment types. The participants had to choose from four statements the one that best describes the way they approach close relationships. Bartholomew and Horowitz (1991) stimulated a two-dimensional understanding of the measurement of relational attachment in the context of the dimensions of avoidance and anxiety. They belong to the most common dimensional questionnaires currently used to measure the relationship Experiences in Close Relationships (ECR; Brennan et al., 1998); The Experiences in Close Relationships, Revised (ECR-R; Fraley et al., 2000); Experiences in Close Relationships, Relationship Structures (ECR-RS; Fraley et al., 2011); Attachment Style Questionnaire (ASQ; Feeney et al., 1994).

Collins and Read (1990) created an 18-item questionnaire to measure attachment dimensions in romantic relationships, the Adult Attachment Scale (AAS), which Neustadt and Furnham (2006) reformulated for relationships with others in the workplace and created Adult Attachment in the Workplace (AAW). They defined a 2-factor solution to insecure attachment in the workplace. Attachment at work was also developed from the theory of environmental psychology and attachment to place. Place attachment used to be measured directly as workplace attachment. It was defined as an emotional bond involving a dynamic interaction between an employee and the organizational environment. It was measured as a one-dimensional construct focusing on the intensity of experiencing this bond (Rioux, 2006). Scrima (2020) defined workplace attachment as an emotional connection between an individual and a workplace that expresses the desire to maintain proximity to the place of work. He described

the final three attachment styles to the workplace, inspired by Bartholomew & Horowitz (1991), as secure, preoccupied, and dismissive.

In addition to questionnaire dimensional measurement, attachment is diagnosed through an interview as a predominant attachment style, with The adult attachment interview (AAI; Hesse, 2008). George and West (2012) created the projective method, The Adult Attachment Projective Picture System: Attachment Theory and Assessment in Adults, which they recommend using as a diagnostic tool for psychodynamically oriented professionals to individually identify deficits and sources of the patient's attachment in therapy.

Study Goal

There is still a need for a graphical tool for identifying attachment styles at work. There is no pictorial questionnaire for measuring attachment in the work environment. A pictorial questionnaire could be more attractive to working adults than the usual self-rating scale. Its advantage is also its semi-projective characteristics when participants are less likely to influence the questionnaire results consciously. This paper aims to present the process of creating a questionnaire for measuring attachment styles in the workplace through pictures. We will start from a combination of a dimensional understanding of the measurement of attachment to significant figures at the workplace (supervisor, colleagues) and a typical understanding of the prevailing behavior in interpersonal relationships (Hazan & Shaver, 1990).

METHOD

Participants

The sample consisted of 129 participants (78% women) aged 19 to 47. 81% of the participants studied at a university, 18% had a university degree, and less than a percent had secondary education. 51% of the participants worked in a private company, 15% in the state or public administration, 3% in a non-profit organization, and the remaining 31% were not working. The total number of employees was 98.

Data collection was carried out online based on the principle of available selection. The research group originally consisted of 139 respondents. Both employed and unemployed people could participate in the research. We excluded ten participants from the research based on incorrectly filled control questions.

Measures

The workplace attachment questionnaire consisted of 13 items: 1. I am not interested in spending as much time with colleagues as others; 2. I avoid relationships with colleagues; 3. I avoid being emotionally close to other people in my work team; 4. I do not like making contact with colleagues; 5. I have a good relationship with my supervisor and feel motivated by them; 6. My supervisor is my motivation and inspiration; 7. I have a good supervisor whom I trust; 8. I can easily talk to my supervisor about my ideas and criticism; 9. I believe my supervisor is a good leader, and I respect their decisions; 10. I need to feel reassured by my colleagues and supervisor; 11. I need to obtain reassurance that I am doing a good job; 12. I need recognition to consider my work valuable; 13. I need reassurance from others whether my performance is sufficient. The questionnaire was originally constructed on the principle of self-assessment, with a 6-point Likert scale from 1 (do not agree at all) to 6 (completely agree).

We matched the pictures to the existing statements by selecting three statements for one picture, one from each dimension. One statement always represented one of the attachment styles. The participant's task was to choose one statement for the picture according to which statement best describes the situation in the picture. The participant thus identified his preferred

attachment style at work. We used 15 pictures and the same trio of statements under each. We thus created four questionnaires, each of which contained 122 items. In this case, the item was formed by combining a picture and three statements. We got the images from the site <https://pixabay.com/sk/>.

The online questionnaire included three attention control questions as well as demographic questions. The participants had the opportunity to express themselves in an open question about the questionnaire items and how it was filled out for them.

Examples of items:

- A) I avoid relationships with colleagues (*Example of avoidant attachment*)
- B) I believe my supervisor is a good leader, and I respect their decisions (*Example of secure attachment*)
- C) I need to obtain reassurance that I am doing a good job (*Example of anxious attachment*)

- A) I need to feel reassured by my colleagues and supervisor. (*Example of anxious attachment*)
- B) I am not interested in spending as much time with colleagues as others. (*Example of avoidant attachment*)
- C) I have a good relationship with my supervisor and feel motivated by them. (*Example of secure attachment*)

Subsequently, we identified the items where the participants chose each statement in the same, with approximately 30% distribution. We eliminated items where any of the statements were preferred by more than 33%. This process ensured that each of the three statements had an equal chance of being chosen by the participants for the given picture. This is how we ensured that a particular picture could differentiate between individuals' statement preferences. We created the main questionnaire from the selected pictures analyzed in this study. It contained 41 items, i.e., pictures with a combination of three statements. We edited these images uniformly in black and white.

Examples of items:

- A) I need recognition to consider my work valuable.
- B) My supervisor is my motivation and inspiration.
- C) I avoid being emotionally close to other people in my work team.

- A) I am not interested in spending as much time with colleagues as others.
- B) I have a good relationship with my supervisor and feel motivated by them.
- C) I need to feel reassured by my colleagues and supervisor.

Data analysis

We applied descriptive, correlational analysis and testing of differences. We worked in programs MS Excel and IBM SPSS 20.

Ethics

The FSEV UK ethics committee approved the research under number 1647-2/2022. Participants confirmed their consent to participate online. They did not suffer any harm while filling out the questionnaires. They were properly informed that they could withdraw from the research without consequences at any time.

RESULTS

We reduced the total of 41 images to 8. We proceeded by selecting only the items in which the participants chose every one of the statements in the range of approximately 30%. For each statement identified in the picture, we counted a point in one of the three scales of the questionnaire. Table 1 contains the Spearman correlation matrix of the subscales and their descriptive data.

Table 1 Correlations, Mean, Standard Deviation, Skewness, and Kurtosis of Items

Variable	1	2	3
1. Secure attachment	—		
2. Anxious attachment	-.366***	—	
3. Avoidant attachment	-.550***	-.493***	—
Mean	2.58	2.81	2.61
Std. Deviation	1.73	1.71	1.83
Skewness	0.61	0.42	0.48
Std. Error of Skewness	0.21	0.21	0.21
Kurtosis	0.22	-0.04	-0.48
Std. Error of Kurtosis	0.42	0.42	0.42
Minimum	0.00	0.00	0.00
Maximum	8.00	8.00	7.00

All scales correlate with each other moderately materially and all negatively (Table 1). Avoidant attachment negatively correlates with both secure ($\rho = -.55$) and anxious ($\rho = -.493$). Secure attachment negatively correlates with anxious attachment ($\rho = -.366$).

Table 2 Wilcoxon Signed-Rank Test

Measure 1	Measure 2	W	Z	df	p	Rank-Biserial Correlation
Secure	- Anxious	2756.500	-1.034	0.298		-0.113
Avoidant	- Anxious	2657.500	-0.720	0.470		-0.080
Secure	- Avoidant	3219.500	-0.164	0.870		-0.018

The participants did not differ in the selection of individual attachment styles. None of the styles stands out above the others (Table 2).

Table 3 Mann-Whitney U test

	W	Df	P	Rank-Biserial Correlation
Secure	1370.500		0.728	0.044
Anxious	967.000		0.036	-0.264
Avoidant	1538.000		0.174	0.171

Note. For the Mann-Whitney test, the effect size is given by the rank biserial correlation.
Women = 1, Men = 2

Women scored statistically significantly higher in anxious attachment, with a small effect size (Table 3).

DISCUSSION

The results of the analysis show that the individual scales of the questionnaire are negatively correlated with each other. Correlations of attachment styles are not rare (Gillath et

al., 2016). However, insecure attachment styles typically correlate positively and negatively with secure attachment styles. Correlations of individual statement frequencies do not reflect relationships between attachment styles but the fact that selections of statements must naturally reflect negative relationships since the more one of the attachment styles is chosen, the less the other attachment styles are preferred. It shows that the Attachment in the workplace questionnaire can discriminate the attachment style typical for an individual. The questionnaire enables us to identify the dominating type of attachment in the individuals. However, not all people should be differentiated in their attachment styles, especially those with 3-3-2 preferences for each scale.

Women scored higher in anxious attachment than men. Women and men typically do not differ in attachment styles (Del Giudice, 2016), only in the context of increased stress. Since we focused on a sample of working adults, most of whom were university students, we can assume that our research sample experienced higher stress levels.

Regarding the research limits, we would suggest repeating images, which the participants complained about and pointed out when filling out the form. Out of the 13 questions, one statement was dropped from the scale of secure attachment to the leader (I can easily talk to my supervisor about my ideas and criticism). Thus, only 12 statements of the workplace attachment questionnaire were assigned to the pictures. The research sample consisted mainly of working students, which could have influenced their perception of the leader and the overlapping of the role of a superior at work with the role of a teacher at school. Working students can also have different reasons for working. Their motivation and needs to work can significantly differ from those of full-time working adults. It would be appropriate to indicate the differences between full and part-time employed and between working students and not studying working adults.

Further research could verify the relationship between Attachment in the workplace questionnaire and other methods measuring attachment. Using pictures during measurement could make filling in the questionnaire more pleasant for the participants and increase its attractiveness. The workplace attachment questionnaire is a semi-projective test which combines the advantages of projective techniques and questionnaires. The adult participants could be more involved in completing the questionnaire and at the same time, less consciously influencing the answers. The pictorial questionnaire assesses not only consciously represented aspects of the individual's attachment at work, but also unconscious.

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APPENDIX

Choose one of the three presented statements that describes the depicted situation best

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/illustrations/sekret%3%a1rka-%c5%beena-kancel%3%a1ria-pr%3%a1ca-7040378/>

- A) I have a good relationship with my supervisor and feel motivated by them.
- B) I am not interested in spending as much time with colleagues as others.
- C) I need to feel reassured by my colleagues and supervisor.

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/illustrations/p%3%a1r-vz%5%a5ah-podnikate%4%be-podnikate%4%beka-3159978/>

- A) I need to feel reassured by my colleagues and supervisor.
- B) I have a good relationship with my supervisor and feel motivated by them.
- C) I am not interested in spending as much time with colleagues as others

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/illustrations/p%3%a1r-vz%5%a5ah-podnikate%4%be-podnikate%4%beka-3159978/>

- A) I need reassurance from others whether my performance is sufficient.
- B) I avoid relationships with colleagues.
- C) I have a good supervisor whom I trust.

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/vectors/%C5%BEena-%C5%BEeny-podnikania-%C5%BEena-%C4%BEud%C3%AD-1353825/>

- A) I need reassurance from others whether my performance is sufficient.
- B) I have a good supervisor whom I trust.
- C) I avoid relationships with colleagues.

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/vectors/%C5%BEena-%C5%BEeny-podnikania-%C5%BEena-%C4%BEud%C3%AD-1353825/>

- A) I need to obtain reassurance that I am doing a good job.

- B) I do not like making contact with colleagues.
- C) I believe my supervisor is a good leader, and I respect their decisions.

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/vectors/pribl%C3%AD%C5%BEEenie-dia%C4%BEkov%C3%A9-stretnutie-7201517/>

- A) I have a good relationship with my supervisor and feel motivated by them.
- B) I need to feel reassured by my colleagues and supervisor.
- C) I am not interested in spending as much time with colleagues as others.

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/illustrations/kari%C3%A9ra-%C5%BEEivotopis-pren%C3%A1jom-pohovor-3478983/>

- A) I need recognition to consider my work valuable.
- B) My supervisor is my motivation and inspiration.
- C) I avoid being emotionally close to other people in my work team.

Picture downloaded from: <https://pixabay.com/sk/vectors/pribl%C3%AD%C5%BEEenie-dia%C4%BEkov%C3%A9-stretnutie-7201517/>

- A) I need recognition to consider my work valuable.
- B) I avoid being emotionally close to other people in my work team.
- C) My supervisor is my motivation and inspiration.

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